

Risks of Artificial Intelligence in Business Management

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Abstract

One actually cannot deny the buzz and hype of Artificial Intelligence in the field of Science, Education, Business Health care, Transport industries etc. Artificial Intelligence is set to revolutionize the way the business men do their jobs, predict the market, and project themselves.

Artificial Intelligence is both boon and bane to the world of business. The list of benefits is a long one but the list of limitations is longer than that. In the early years when artificial Intelligence was newly introduced to the field of business there was extensive usage in all the functions of the business. Over dependence on technology has given rise to the risk factor. The first thing that usage of Artificial Intelligence leads to is no control over one’s own business, the other things that follow are issues like high cost, technological complexity, over transparency, no privacy to the customers, inequality in distribution of wealth, artificial stupidity, no accountability and no human touch.

As researchers we should bear in mind that scale of problems in Artificial Intelligence that can be beyond exponential, our energy source and our ability to observe the world are always finite and thus the result in terms of ordinary human experience are likely less impressive than they sound.

Keywords: Hype, limitations, lack of control, dependence, and complexities.

Introduction

Evolving World of Learning Machines is Artificial Intelligence. Automation and Innovation have very different potential implication for both the future of Human and Business progress. Artificial Intelligence creates a powerful frictional image that serves to both inspire innovation and evoke fear. Narrow Artificial Intelligence can be integrated to produce highly powerful application.

General Artificial Intelligence refers to a machine that is capable of performing the broad array of intellectual tasks of a human. Artificial Intelligence. A logarithms are widely used in all the fields of business and daily life right from managing finance to managing cars.

Computer Systems are becoming Common at work places and have occupied the central place in most of the top businesses, Government Departments, Military Organizations, Health care centers and so on

Business Houses have made extensive use of Artificial Intelligence in their organizations to cope with the unpredictable eventually of an ever changing volatile worlds.

Objective of the Study

1. To list out the Risks of employing Artificial Intelligence in Marketing Management,
2. To list out the Risks of employing Artificial Intelligence in Human Resource Management and
3. To list out the Risks of employing Artificial Intelligence in Finance Management

Analytical View

Risk is an event or condition that if it occurs has a positive or negative effect on Project Objectives. In this paper we will throw light on the implementation of Artificial Intelligence in department of the Marketing, Human Resource and Finance.

There are 2 common characteristics of Risk in Business

1. Risk represents a future event.
2. The risk has a probability of occurring of greater than 100%.

Management of Marketing, Human Resource and Finance Functions are the major tasks of any kind of Business be it small or Big. Use of Artificial Intelligence in these Departments is due to the it's unique features like

1. Speed of execution.
2. Operational Ability.
3. Accuracy.
4. Error Reduction.
5. Difficult Exploration.
6. Work Efficiency.

Artificial Intelligence in Marketing Management

Artificial Intelligence Marketing is a form of direct marketing leveraging database marketing techniques as well as Artificial Intelligence concept and model such as machine learning and Bayesian Network. It helps in giving Standard Solutions to the Standard Problems.

Major areas where Artificial Intelligence is used are:

- a. Product Management namely Search in the areas of new products, branding and packaging;
- b. Promotion management namely, sales forecasting, website designing, image positioning;
- c. Market and consumer management namely, customer segmentation, predictive customer service and preventing fraud and data breaches

Finding: 1

Modern Marketing Management employs Extensive use of Artificial Intelligence. Marketing Management requires lot of innovation , creativity , pooling of ideas and brainstorming sessions for positive outcome for the company .But now what has happened is Artificial Intelligence is performing all the functions leaving way for the occurrence of the risk factor in the future of the company. Marketing conversation has become a human machine conversation, the essence of the marketing is the conversation between a Business and its customers and potential customers and this has been a marketing tenet for a long time. But it is lost due to AI. Integration Challenges and lack of understanding of the market and sales are also the ill effects of Artificial intelligent.

Marketing hugely depends on Principal of Perception and Reasoning which cannot be done with the help of AI. AI based marketing uses complex set of means and techniques to perform complex functions but this does not help in understanding the complex behavior of its customers.

To perform all the functions of humans and to adapt to the changing business environment Creation of Smart Technologies and, software programs upgrading on regular basis is required. Artificial Intelligence will not take place of a marketing team because it cannot replace creative thinking as it is just a manmade program and does not have new ideas it can only make variations on the existing program.

Modern Marketers can be advised to take help of AI to do the routine jobs and thus reduce task burden and rather focus on improving the business.

Artificial Intelligence in Human Resource Management

Integration of machines into Work life leading to Automatic Administration is the meaning of Artificial Intelligence in Human resource Management.

The growing importance of all the functions in the Business and in keeping the economy healthy and shining the spot light is on the activities of the Human resource dept. The main objective of the HR manager is to develop a thorough knowledge of corporate culture, plans, and policies, to act as an internal change agent and consultant, to initiate change and act as an expert and facilitator, to actively keep communication lines open, to evolve HR strategies and to diagnose problems and suggest a solution.

The Basic Functions of the HR Dept. is Attract, Engage, Retain and Develop Work Force required for the organization.

In the modern organization Artificial Intelligence is widely involved in Hiring, Engaging and Developing the Humans employed in the organization.

Hiring now a days is done through Professional working Sites and job boards, on line applications system is adopted to gather, screen and manage massive applications. The same technology assists in selection of the Best candidates and eliminate the worst. Artificial Intelligence actually Spots, Screens, and Rank Applications.

Engaging the candidates is technically done through automated e mails or messaging workflows. Along with engaging, re engaging is also done to determine the interest level, work experience or skills the candidate possess.

Retaining the employees is the most important function of the HR dept. Artificial Intelligence helps to perform this function by individual skill management, internal management, and standard Performance Analysis.

Development and Training by employing technology is done by scheduling best time frame and best technique for overall development of the employ which is preparing the work force for the future.

Finding: 2

The idea of Machines replacing Human beings sounds wonderful. It appears to save us from the pain but is it so exciting? Idea like working whole heartedly with sense of Belonging and working with dedication have no existence in the world of artificial intelligence. All the functions related to HR requires human intelligence along with emotional intellectual which guides their feelings and thoughts towards attending work and addressing the issues. BUT this is not the case with machines the intuitive abilities that humans possess the way humans can judge based on previous knowledge the inherent abilities that they have cannot be replicate by machines also the machines lack common sense.

HR Leaders and Practitioners need to have a clear understanding that Hiring, Engaging, Developing and Retaining cannot be done with a Standardized Format. In an organization the employees are varied in nature and different personalized approach is required to manage them for example the same Training Technique and the same Performance Analysis technique will not be suitable for all the employees thus creating problems to Attrition in the organization.

Artificial Intelligence in Financial Management

Artificial Intelligences greatest advances have yet to come but the combination of Big Data with machine learning algorithms has already yields benefit to financial world daily operations Artificial Intelligence is redefining the financial management landscape increasingly financial organization are adapting a machine learning based approach to augment their algorithmic rules based approach towards surveillance and risk management .

This progress in technology is also propelled by the enormous volume of data from customers and market players with the automation as well as digitalization of financial services, Banking, Insurance, and Trading. Data explosion is clearly the key enabler .One can dive into more than 10 years of Banking, insurance Mortgage and Financial Trading history for every single of the million traction that takes place daily.

Artificial Intelligence is Widely used in the Functioning of the Financial Department: Namely

1. Asset Management: AI identifies pattern and indexes via social network and helps in effective Asset Management.
2. Fraud detection: AI uses the data available to construct applicable algorithms to offer insight improve decisions mitigate risk and detect minor to major anomalies to prevent fraud or disasters.
3. Regulatory Compliance: AI helps in recovering layers of documentation or data to meet regulatory policies.
4. Market Data and Research: AI helps to index and select financial data and then supply it in the form of report articles newsletters and even personalized web sites all automated.
5. International Trade: AI helps on web and digital space crawling to map buyers and suppliers data to generate leads for contacting potential clients
6. Virtual Customer Services Assistance: AI improves customer support and counselling by combining Big Data and machine learning.

Finding: 3

AI is relentlessly focusing on being customer centric, improving the operations, cost management, focuses on profitability, Explores new ways of generating alpha and claim management. All the Above mentioned applications of AI are proneto limitations. Financial players should pay more attention to the security, privacy of customer's data. Imperfections in AI need to be resolved. Limited availability of right quality and quantity of Data insufficient understanding of AI also leads to losses in the organizations .Over utilization of AI acts as a barrier to the culture of the organization. Proper utilization of AI requires skilled Data Scientists and relevant talent to manage Digital FinancialManagement.

Conclusion

Artificial Intelligence is like a two edge sword it ultimately serves as a tool to achieve maximum efficiency of Business The purpose of Artificial Intelligence is to augment human capabilities instead of completely replacing it. Artificial Intelligence tools compliment HR capabilities but

do not design the structure as that will require strategic human planning and vision. Artificial Intelligent has direct tangible impact on Moral, Motivation and degree of engagement for human resource. Rather than blindly apply Artificial Intelligence to all the areas of management it is advisable to adopt it in jobs which does not involve human thoughtfulness, reasoning, people skills, soft skills, and strategic planning, human instinct for creative solutions.

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